

Central Washington University, Business and Community Services

Regional Sustainability Gap Index (RSGI): A Measure of Regional Sustainability Through Human Capital

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Prepared By: Rob Ogburn, MBA, William Provaznik, PhD., Central Washington University, and Coco Wu, PhD, Tennessee Technological University.

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Executive Summary

The Regional Sustainability Gap Index (RSGI) is a new measure designed to assess whether a region is on a sustainable economic path for its residents. The index combines two components: M_i , a measure of the current wage gap between a county and the most economically active county in the state, and R_i , a measure of each county's wage-growth trajectory relative to that most active county. Together, these reveal not only a region's present wage altitude, but also the direction in which that wage horizon is moving. In Washington State's case, M_i measures the distance between a county's median wages and King County's median wages, which represent the wage frontier of the State. King County's wages represent the wage frontier because it contains the state's densest concentration of high-value industries.

M_i captures the immediate gap in purchasing power that shapes a community's present ability to support its residents.

R_i identifies whether that gap is widening or narrowing, which is a forward-looking signal that affects the choices young people, families, workers, and employers make about education, training, investment, and mobility.

Low M_i counties already struggle to sustain local families. When low M_i is paired with a low or declining R_i , the region becomes increasingly unsustainable. Declining wage trajectories reshape expectations about the future, erode hope and collective efficacy, and change the population and industry structure over time. These processes influence whether a young person can reasonably envision building a stable future in their home community or must leave in search of opportunity elsewhere.

The RSGI provides Washington State with a clear metric for understanding long-term regional divergence, identifying where wage horizons are collapsing, and highlighting the counties where strategic intervention is most urgently needed.

1) Introduction: The Role and Limitations of Conventional Indicators

Regional leaders in Washington State face a growing challenge: conventional economic indicators paint a picture of statewide prosperity, yet many counties are experiencing declining household purchasing power, shrinking opportunities, and widening wage gaps relative to the state's strongest economic region. Existing metrics such as GDP, employment totals, or overall wage averages are effective at measuring the *scale* of an economy, but they are less effective at revealing whether prosperity is being sustained within communities. As noted by the OECD's *Rural Well-Being: Geography of Opportunities* (2020), these output-based measures often obscure the lived experience of regions where affordability, opportunity, and household resilience are diverging from statewide or national aggregates.

This limitation is well documented. Regional economists have shown that production-centered metrics often fail to capture declines in median well-being, particularly in rural areas where output may rise even as inequality widens, labor markets hollow out, and household incomes stagnate (Sutton et al., 2023; Partridge & Rickman, 2008; Johnson & Lichter, 2019; Butler et al., 2020). Such divergences are not simply numerical artifacts. They have structural consequences. Research on rural population change demonstrates that regions with weak wage growth tend to lose younger and higher-skill workers, experience long-term erosion of their tax base, and become increasingly dependent on low-margin, non-exporting industries (Carr & Kefalas, 2009; Li, 2023; Bjerke, 2022). Over time, these dynamics contribute to what economic geographers describe as regional "lock-in," in which policy frameworks reward short-term production over adaptive capacity, further weakening long-term competitiveness (Martin & Sunley, 2006; Hassink, 2010; OECD, 2020).

For Washington State, these structural patterns leave local governments without clear tools to evaluate how their communities are performing relative to the economic forces shaping them. National and international metrics like the BEA's Regional Price Parity or the OECD's Regional Well-Being Index provide broad comparisons, but they do not account for the internal wage dynamics among Washington's counties or the growing divergence between metro and non-metro economies. As a result, policymakers lack a measure capable of capturing both current wage position and future wage trajectory within the state.

The Regional Sustainability Gap Index (RSGI) is designed to fill this gap. By combining a county's wage altitude (M_i) with its wage-growth trajectory (R_i), the RSGI measures both where a community stands today and where its wage horizon is headed. This dual focus allows stakeholders to see whether a county is on a sustainable path.

Section 2: Metropolitan Wage Ratio (M_i):

M_i represents the current wage position of a county relative to the state's wage leader. It captures how far above or below the state's most competitive region a county's median wage stands today. This measure reflects the long-standing finding that regional wage levels are shaped by industry composition, competitive structure, and the ability of local firms to create and retain value within the community (Porter, 1990; Isserman, Feser, & Warren, 2009; Boschma & Iammarino, 2009).

Counties with a high M_i typically have a concentration of industries that compete successfully in external markets, capture higher margins, and support skilled labor. These regions tend to have stronger internal business ecosystems, more diversified base industry clusters that export high-value services and goods, and value chains that retain a larger share of the wealth generated locally. In contrast, counties with lower M_i values often have limited exposure to export-oriented industries, higher dependence on low-margin or externally owned firms, and fewer opportunities for workers to access high-wage occupations. Research on base industries and import-replacing sectors underscores how this structural composition shapes wage outcomes across regions (Jacobs, 1969; Besser, 2013; Goetz, Fleming, & Rupasingha, 2018).

M_i matters because it reflects more than a static wage comparison. It captures the structural conditions that shape a community's ability to support families today. Regions with low M_i values face immediate affordability challenges. Even if jobs are available, their wages often fall short of the cost of housing, childcare, healthcare, and essential goods that are often priced by market factors outside their region. Household incomes in these regions are commonly sustained by multiple earners or multiple jobs, signaling a structural gap between local wages and economic stability. This condition significantly overrepresents prosperity in distressed areas when evaluated by traditional measures because the cost of maintaining adequate living standards requires more labor input per household than in higher-wage regions. Counting household income masks the underlying definitions of and efforts within the household that local residents have adjusted to accommodate the economic pressures they face.

In strategic terms, Mi tells us how competitive a county is right now in attracting and retaining skilled workers. Families make relocation decisions based not only on career opportunities but also on whether the local wage structure can support a sustainable life. A low Mi signals that a region is already behind in the competition for talent and that households face immediate pressure that undermines long-term retention.

Regions with a low Mi start at lower altitudes. High Mi regions begin from a position of strength. Knowing where a county is starting from (Mi) is critical for knowing the conditions impacting where it is going (Ri).

Section 3: Relative Growth Ratio (Ri)

Ri is a future-oriented indicator. It measures whether a county's wage trajectory is keeping pace with the state's economic frontier (King County). Past experiences build a basis for expectations about the future. These are the patterns that communities and their members interpret to make choices about whether investing in education, skills, or entrepreneurship will pay off. When Ri is rising, residents anticipate more options, more investment, and more opportunities ahead. Even if current conditions are difficult, a rising trajectory promises a tomorrow with a broader set of possibilities. When Ri declines, residents observe tangible evidence that the future is narrowing. Empty lots, shuttered shops, and buildings repurposed into low-value uses signal that long-term investments carry greater risk and lower expected return. A declining Ri therefore communicates that the ceiling on what the community can offer is falling, and that future degrees of freedom are shrinking.

Low Ri affects the regional community in three interrelated ways, each of which is well supported by the regional sociology, education, and economic geography research.

3.1 Low Ri collapses future expectations.

A large body of research shows that young people form educational and occupational plans based on the opportunity structure they observe in their immediate surroundings. Niccolai, Damaske, and Park (2022) describe this as "expectations of place," where youth assess whether their region can realistically reward education or advanced skills. When local wage trajectories stagnate or decline, students see fewer viable pathways upward and adjust their aspirations accordingly.

Workforce technology literacy is a strong asset for regional competitiveness and growth, and is a priority in Washington State's strategic focus. However, in distressed communities, similar patterns mentioned above are seen in youth STEM participation. Saw

and Agger (2021; 2024) find that rural and small-town students' STEM course-taking and college decisions depend heavily on whether high-skill opportunities appear attainable in their regional labor market. In low-Ri communities, STEM preparation appears disconnected from local jobs, reducing the perceived payoff for engaging in difficult coursework. Conversely, the expectations from living in a declining community are well documented as factoring in youth's rational calculations in their choice of risky behaviors (Rung & Madden, 2018), such as alcohol consumption in early adolescence (McDade, et al., 2011) and crime (Clinkinbeard, 2013).

While the majority of rural residents would prefer to stay in their communities (Carr & Kefalas, 2009), the perceived future of the region fundamentally shapes who stays and who leaves. Domina and Thurston (2006) show that highly educated and high-ability youth are the most likely to leave nonmetropolitan areas, and that outmigration is strongly tied to economic incentives. The most significant attractors are the higher returns to education available in metropolitan labor markets. In their analysis of national migration patterns from 1989 to 2004, they find that rural BA-holders became increasingly likely to migrate to metro areas, while metropolitan BA-holders became less likely to migrate to rural regions. This selective pattern reinforces a widening gap: those who see limited local rewards for education leave, while those who stay tend to scale down their ambitions to match local wage trajectories.

A critical takeaway from research is that low Ri reshapes expectations about what the future can hold. It influences educational investment, career planning, and the likelihood of outmigration among the most capable youth, while increasing present-oriented behavior and reducing long-term skill formation among those who remain.

3.2 Low Ri erodes community-level hope and efficacy.

Economic decline not only changes expectations but also undermines the psychological foundations needed for long-term investment. Sampson et al. (1997) show that weakening economic conditions reduce collective efficacy. This is the shared belief that a community can act together to improve its circumstances. As wage trajectories decline, residents see fewer examples of upward mobility or successful reinvestment, eroding confidence that effort will matter locally.

This aligns with work on wage insecurity and future orientation. Kalleberg and Marsden (2013) show that when workers perceive unstable or stagnant wages, they become less willing to invest in long-term skill development and more likely to adopt short-term strategies. In low-Ri regions, this short-term orientation towards life planning becomes

rational behavior. The uncertainties and risk the residents face sharply discounts the future value the personal investments needed for successful collective action (Venkatesh, 2006).

Hope theory explains why these psychological dynamics matter: as Snyder (2002) shows, hope consists of both agency (“I can do it”) and pathways (“there is a way to do it”) Luthans (2002) demonstrated how hope plays a critical role in workforce development and management settings. This also extends to the collective sense of friend groups and families’ sense of being able to pursue individual and collective adaptive strategies (Bernardo, 2010). Declining regions erode both hope factors: agency declines when effort is rarely rewarded, and pathways narrow when communities fail to generate new high-value opportunities.

Entrepreneurship research reinforces this point in the formation of new, high-value businesses, as well as the business/product and technology development and adoption needed for existing businesses to be more competitive. Loi, Martínez-Gregorio, Barbieri, and Fayolle (2025) find that hope and optimism, being the key components of Psychological Capital (PsyCap), are strongly associated with the likelihood of engaging in high-value entrepreneurial activity. Low-Ri regions depress these psychological drivers, reducing both the supply of entrepreneurs and the quality of ventures launched.

Low Ri produces a psychological contraction. The community’s collective capacity to envision and pursue a better future diminishes, further lowering the region’s potential for renewal. In general, Ri quantifies whether a county is catching up to or falling behind the state’s wage frontier.

3.3 Low Ri alters the region’s population and economic structure.

Over time, weak wage trajectories reshape who stays, who leaves, and what kinds of industries remain viable. Selective out-migration is one of the most consistent findings in rural sociology. Carr and Kefalas (2009) and Cromartie, von Reichert, and Arthun (2015) show that high-skill youth and college-bound workers leave regions with weak economic futures, while those with fewer perceived options remain. Li (2023) demonstrates that wage differentials across metro–nonmetro boundaries are key predictors of movement, with workers gravitating toward regions offering stronger wage horizons. Sowl, Witte, and Lee (2021) find that returning to rural areas after college is contingent on whether local wages can support long-term economic stability.

These population shifts feed into structural economic effects. Research on regional lock-in shows that declining regions become increasingly specialized in low-margin sectors and lose the adaptive capacity to reorganize toward higher-value activities (Hassink, 2010; Hu &

Hassink, 2020). Martin and Sunley (2006) argue that such path dependence is difficult to reverse without significant external intervention. Isserman, Feser, and Warren (2009) identify similar dynamics in rural counties that fail to diversify or upgrade their industry base. Waters and Shuttles (2022) show how declining regions experience structural “tightness” that restricts their ability to absorb new industries or innovation.

The result is a self-reinforcing cycle: low Ri weakens the labor force, which discourages new industry formation, which in turn lowers wage trajectories further. Over time, the region becomes increasingly dependent on low-value, low-wage sectors, narrowing its development pathways.

Section 4: Analytical Impacts of Low Mi and Low Ri

Mi and Ri together describe a county’s economic position and trajectory. Mi captures the *current* wage altitude of a region relative to the statewide leader, while Ri indicates whether that gap is widening or narrowing over time. The interaction of the two measures has predictable and well-documented effects on regional economic sustainability.

4.1 Impacts of Low Mi (Present Wage Altitude)

Counties with low Mi values face immediate structural disadvantages. Median wages fall below the level required to support household stability, imposing higher labor input per household (multiple earners, multiple jobs) to achieve equivalent living standards. This aligns with research showing that low-wage regions experience higher levels of household stress, limited consumption capacity, and reduced discretionary income. These factors serve to further suppress already low local demand and weaken the regional multiplier effect (Goetz et al., 2018; Partridge & Rickman, 2008; Johnson & Lichter, 2019).

Low Mi also reduces a region’s competitiveness in attracting and retaining workers with high-return skill sets. Skilled labor is sensitive to wage floors and tends to relocate toward regions where wages exceed household cost burdens. Empirical work demonstrates that regions with persistently low median wages experience reduced labor-force attachment, lower rates of skill formation, and increased internal migration toward higher-wage labor markets (Li, 2023; Bjerke, 2022). As a result, low Mi reflects an immediate affordability gap and signals structural weakness in the region’s current labor-market capacity.

4.2 Impacts of Low Ri (Future Wage Trajectory)

Ri captures whether a county's wages are converging with or diverging from the state's wage frontier. While Mi captures present conditions, Ri indicates whether a county's wage environment is improving or deteriorating relative to the state's most competitive region. Extensive evidence demonstrates that wage trajectories influence future expectations, household planning, and local investment behavior (Niccolai et al., 2022; Saw & Agger, 2021; Domina & Thurston, 2006). When Ri is low or declining, families, workers, and firms anticipate a narrowing opportunity structure.

Declining wage trajectories are associated with lower investment in education and skill acquisition, reduced entrepreneurial activity, and weakened institutional capacity (Kalleberg & Marsden, 2013; Loi et al., 2025). In regional terms, low Ri counties face reduced rates of business formation, slower industry diversification, and diminished ability to recruit or retain firms in high-value sectors. Over time, this produces a structural shift toward lower-productivity industries and decreases the region's adaptive capacity (Hassink, 2010; Martin & Sunley, 2006).

4.3 Combined Effects of Low Mi and Low Ri

Low Mi and low Ri together indicate a region that is both behind today and falling further behind tomorrow. Regions exhibiting both characteristics tend to experience:

1. **Shrinking labor-force quality:** this is driven by selective out-migration of high-skill workers and lower human-capital investment among those who remain (Carr & Kefalas, 2009; Cromartie et al., 2015).
2. **Reduced fiscal capacity:** due to low-wage regions generating lower per-capita tax revenues, reducing the ability to invest in workforce development, infrastructure, and institutional supports.
3. **Industry downgrading:** this happens as firms in high-value sectors avoid jurisdictions with weak present wages and weak future wage trajectories.
4. **Accelerated path dependence:** seen in low-wage, low-growth conditions, locks regions into low-margin industries, further reducing competitiveness (Hu & Hassink, 2020; Isserman et al., 2009).

The combined effect is a measurable drop in regional sustainability. Counties with low Mi but rising Ri retain potential for future recovery. Counties with low Ri but higher Mi may sustain household well-being in the short term while facing long-term transition pressures. Counties with both low Mi and low Ri face the most acute long-term risk, as they lack both

the present wage altitude and the future wage momentum necessary to support workforce retention, skill development, and economic resilience.

4.4 Analytical Transition to Empirical Illustration

The Adams County case (below) provides a concrete example of these dynamics. Adams County illustrates how M_i and R_i translate into projected wage trajectories and lifetime economic outcomes.

Section 5: Empirical Illustration - Adams County, Washington

Adams County: A Child Born into a Shrinking Wage Future

Adams County has the lowest RSGI in Washington State. Its position at the bottom of the index makes it the clearest illustration of what long-term wage divergence means in the life of a single community and its next generation. The RSGI is a structural measure that blends both the metropolitan wage gap and the county's future growth velocity. The following analysis shows what the lowest RSGI score looks like when projected into the life of a child born in Adams County today. It connects the numerical components of the index to the lived experience of shrinking purchasing power, lower wage trajectories, and the early expectation formation that shapes education and career pathways. Because Adams County has both a low current wage altitude (M_i) and one of the weakest wage-growth trajectories (R_i) in the state, it provides the clearest illustration of long-term divergence.

A particularly devastating challenge for rural areas is the way wage erosion and the resulting limited opportunities shape the expectations of younger generations. Youth in rural regions look to their parents, larger family, and the career availability in the community when making their present and future education choices. As we see with the RSGI across nearly all counties in Washington State, most local jobs in many counties are low-wage, and are trending lower.

When the best local jobs barely keep up with the cost of living, young people begin to make calculations about what kind of future is realistic. In their assessment, the present value of hard work has little bearing on their future. Unfortunately, there are many data points available to confirm their beliefs.

As recent research shows, rural adolescents develop what Niccolai, Damaske, and Park (2022) describe as "expectations of place." These are internal assessments about what kinds of futures are possible based on what they observe in their immediate surroundings.

When they see parents and neighbors working multiple jobs with little stability or upward mobility, they absorb the message that local opportunity is scarce and that education or training may not have a clear payoff close to home. These perceptions form early, often by middle school, and influence which subjects they take (Saw & Agger, 2021), whether they plan to attend college (Carr & Kefalas, 2009), and if they imagine staying or leaving the region (Domina & Thurston, 2006; Ashley et al., 2022).

This process has direct consequences for the future competitiveness of communities like Adams County. When young people expect that advanced skills will not be rewarded locally, they often disengage from challenging coursework, particularly in STEM subjects that appear disconnected from local employment options. Those who expect to leave tend to invest in transferable skills that can be used elsewhere, while those who expect to stay often scale back their educational ambitions. Over time, this creates a self-reinforcing cycle: limited opportunity discourages investment in education, and low educational attainment reinforces the limits of opportunity.

For Adams County, Washington, the implications of this situation are profound. A child born today is entering a labor market where the local wage (\$55,536) is already below the benchmark median (\$135,075) and is projected to fall further behind if current conditions persist into 2047, when the child is 22 years old, to \$37,190 (in 2025 dollars). The county's median wage growth has not kept pace with inflation or with the state's innovation-driven regions.

Adjusted to 2025 dollars, the future wage of an Adams County worker amounts to a median wage of \$37,190, or \$18.60 an hour. On January 1st 2026, the Washington State minimum wage will increase to \$17.13 per hour. On the current trajectory, more than half of Adams County workers will be making near minimum wage levels of salaries. Recent wage models put \$20.19 per hour as minimum living wage for Adams County (Glasmeier, 2025). This means the median wage in Adams County is on track to fall below a sustainable living standard.

Without intervention, that child will grow up in a community where most full-time work opportunities may not provide economic security. The long-term consequence is not just lower income, but an inherited expectation that success requires either leaving or compromising the professional and family horizons that youth in other regions take for granted.

We can model what the wage expectation of a child born today would be when they enter their "salad days" and anticipate how they see what their role (if any) in their community looks like when they are 22 years old. From there, we can model what the cost of a one year

delay in changing the trajectory of Adams County's future M_i by raising the R_i to match the R of the leading county.

Cost of Delay: Adams County Example

To illustrate the consequences of delayed action, we model the expected earnings of a child born in Adams County in 2025. The child enters the workforce at age 22, in the year 2047.

We compare two scenarios:

- Scenario A (Immediate Action): The county begins improving its wage trajectory today.
- Scenario B (One-Year Delay): The county delays initiating wage-improving actions by one year.

In this model, the difference between these two scenarios at workforce entry becomes the worker's permanent wage penalty.

Assumptions

- Current median wage (2025):
 $w_0 = \$55,536$
- Adams County real wage growth (2013–2023):
 $g_0 = 1.1397\%$
- Frontier (King County) real wage growth:
 $g_1 = 3.3479\%$
- Transition period to reach frontier trajectory:
10 years
- Workforce entry: age 22
- Career length: 44 working years (ages 22–65)

Why the wage formulas differ

- In Scenario A, Adams County shifts onto the higher g_1 trajectory earlier, giving the worker more total years of higher growth before age 22.
- In Scenario B, the improvement begins one year later, giving fewer years of high-growth wage compounding.

Scenario A: Immediate action

$$w_A(22) = w_0(1 + g_o)^{10} (1 + g_I)^{12}$$
$$w_A(22) = \$92,345$$

Scenario B (One Year Delay):

$$w_B(22) = w_0(1 + g_o)^{11} (1 + g_I)^{11}$$
$$w_B(22) = \$90,371$$

Entry Wage Penalty for delay:

$$\Delta w_{\text{entry}} = w_A(22) - w_B(22)$$
$$\Delta w_{\text{entry}} = \$1,973$$

Lifetime Penalty

Under conservative assumptions, this penalty does not compound. It is repeated evenly across the worker's 44-year career:

$$\text{Lifetime Loss} = 44 \times \Delta w_{\text{entry}}$$
$$\text{Lifetime Loss} = \$86,816$$

Cost of delaying actions for improvement:

$$\frac{\text{Lifetime Loss}}{8760} = \frac{\$86,816}{8760} = \$9.91/\text{hour}$$

The calculations shown for Adams County generate the first of the two components that make up the Regional Sustainability Gap Index (RSGI). This is the Purchasing Power Ratio (PPR), which measures how well local wages maintain real value against inflation. The second component, the Metro Wage Ratio (MWR), compares each county's projected wages to those of King County, representing the state's high-value economic core.

Together, these two ratios capture both internal and external sustainability: the ability of residents to maintain their purchasing power and to remain competitive within Washington’s broader wage hierarchy.

The RSGI is calculated as a simple weighted average of these two components, with M_i receiving twice the weight of R_i because the divergence from metropolitan wages has a larger structural effect on long-term regional competitiveness. The formula used in the spreadsheet is:

$$RSGI_i = \frac{2 \times M_i + R_i}{3}$$

This structure allows the index to reflect both the distance a county has fallen behind the state’s wage leaders and the county’s future ability to close that gap through its internal wage growth.

For **Adams County**, the values of $M_i = 0.67$ and $R_i = 0.19$.

Applying the formula gives:

$$RSGI_i = \frac{2 \times M_i + R_i}{3} = .51$$

This same method was applied to all 39 Washington counties to generate the statewide RSGI chart, which is presented in the following section.

Values are expressed in 2025 dollars, assuming a constant 3% annual inflation rate and continuation of the 2013–2023 wage trend.

County	Lifetime Loss with 1-Yr Delay	Annual Salary Impact 1-Yr Delay	Cost of 1-Hour Delay	Intervention Today: Real Purchasing Power (2047 vs. Today in 2025 \$'s)	Intervention 1 Yr Delay: Real Purchasing Power (2047 vs. Today in 2025 \$'s)
Adams	\$86,816	\$1,973	\$9.91	33.1 %	32.4%
King	\$0	\$0	\$0	0 %	0 %
Spokane	\$74,090	\$1,684	\$3.95	45.8 %	45.0%

County	Lifetime Loss with 1-Yr Delay	Annual Salary Impact 1-Yr Delay	Cost of 1-Hour Delay	Intervention Today: Real Purchasing Power (2047 vs. Today in 2025 \$'s)	Intervention 1 Yr Delay: Real Purchasing Power (2047 vs. Today in 2025 \$'s)
Yakima	\$65,296	\$1,484	\$7.45	36.3 %	35.7%

Section 6: Implications for Washington State Regional Strategy

The RSGI identifies systematic divergence in wage altitude (Mi) and wage trajectory (Ri) across Washington’s counties. These divergences have direct implications for the state’s capacity to maintain a competitive and balanced regional economy. Because wage structure influences workforce retention, human capital development, and industry evolution, counties with low Mi and low Ri represent points of strategic vulnerability in the statewide economic system.

6.1 Workforce Development and Retention

Counties with low Mi face immediate challenges in retaining workers, while counties with low Ri face long-term challenges in keeping workers who expect upward mobility. When both Mi and Ri are low, the capacity to sustain a skilled labor force is sharply reduced. State-level workforce investments (including K–12 STEM efforts, community-college programming, and apprenticeship pipelines) have lower returns in counties where wage trajectories signal limited future payoff. These counties may require targeted interventions that include efforts to promote integration into higher-value industry supply chains available in the larger region, and higher-value entrepreneurship and local business development, to ensure that workforce development programs translate into local retention.

6.2 Industry Recruitment and Competitiveness

Industry location models show that firms in higher-value, higher-wage sectors are sensitive to both current wage floors and expected future labor force quality. While low-Mi counties possess a wage cost advantage, they still struggle to attract firms that rely on skilled labor because of the absence of an available skill “cluster” that would facilitate new operations in the community. Given that nearly all of the low Mi counties in the WA region are also a

low Ri region, a large portion of their potential skilled workforce has either physically “moved out” of the region, or educationally “checked out” while remaining. The RSGI allows the state to identify where industry recruitment strategies may be most constrained and where investments in workforce or infrastructure may yield the most significant marginal benefit.

6.3 Fiscal Capacity and Regional Investment Prioritization

Counties with persistently low Mi and low Ri exhibit weaker per-capita tax bases and limited capacity to finance workforce, infrastructure, and economic development initiatives. This constrains their ability to respond to structural change or capitalize on emerging opportunities. The RSGI provides state agencies with a tool for prioritizing fiscal support where local tax capacity is insufficient to address long-term divergence. This has direct implications for the allocation of grants, capital funds, technical assistance, and matching requirements.

6.4 Long-Term Regional Sustainability

Persistent divergence in Mi and Ri increases the probability of long-term regional imbalance. In Washington, this divergence reinforces a pattern of declining wage altitude and weak wage trajectories. These regions face the highest sustainability risk because their current wages are insufficient to support households, and their future wage pathways show limited capacity for improvement. The RSGI highlights this structural divide and provides a framework for aligning state policy with the specific conditions facing Washington’s most vulnerable counties.

6.5 Strategic Planning Alignment

Washington’s regional planning processes, such as CEDS development, Growth Management Planning, workforce planning, and broadband or infrastructure investment, often rely on qualitative assessments of strengths and weaknesses. The RSGI provides a quantitative framework that can align these planning processes with measurable wage dynamics extending into the larger region. Incorporating Mi and Ri into regional strategic planning efforts allows counties to:

1. Identify structural wage gaps;
2. Assess whether local investments are likely to retain or grow human capital;

3. Prioritize initiatives that improve long-term sustainability rather than short-term activity.

The RSGI complements existing planning tools by grounding strategic priorities in the underlying economic conditions shaping regional futures.

6.6 Statewide Competitiveness

State-level competitiveness depends on the performance of its constituent regions. As counties diverge in wage altitude and wage trajectory, statewide economic resilience becomes increasingly uneven. The RSGI highlights where divergence is accelerating and provides a basis for coordinated intervention aimed at reducing long-term sustainability gaps. In this way, the index supports a more integrated, data-driven approach to statewide economic strategy.

Section 7: Value, Power, and Regional Wage Structure

The wage patterns captured by M_i and R_i reflect deeper structural dynamics related to how regions create, capture, and retain economic value. In regional economic theory, value creation is associated with the ability of firms and industries to produce outputs that command prices above their input costs. In contrast, value capture refers to the extent to which that surplus remains within the region's households, firms, and institutions. M_i and R_i together provide an indicator of how effectively a region participates in this value process.

7.1 Value Creation and Industry Structure

Regions with higher M_i typically contain industries positioned in value-added segments of their supply chains. These industries exhibit higher labor productivity, higher margins, and greater capacity for reinvestment. Industry-mix research shows that regions specializing in such sectors tend to generate higher earnings and greater internal multipliers (Porter, 1990; Boschma & Iammarino, 2009). Conversely, counties with low M_i often rely on industries characterized by low margins, high price sensitivity, and limited opportunities for workers to progress into higher-paying roles. These structural differences contribute directly to current wage level.

7.2 Value Capture and Leakage

A region's ability to retain the value created by its firms influences household incomes and long-term competitiveness. When ownership, managerial decision-making, or profit centers reside outside the region, a larger share of surplus value "leaks" out rather than circulating through local wages, local spending, or local reinvestment. This leakage is consistent with observed patterns in many low-Mi counties, where externally owned firms and thin local supply chains limit the degree to which economic activity translates into higher local wages (Goetz et al., 2018). Over time, reduced value capture contributes to stagnant household earnings and weak wage-growth trajectories.

7.3 Power, Pricing, and Bargaining Dynamics

Wage structures also reflect power asymmetries within regional labor markets. Firms operating in high-margin industries have greater scope to pay higher wages, while firms in cost-constrained sectors have limited bargaining space regardless of labor quality. Commoditized industries such as agriculture, forestry, mining and extraction have low or no product differentiation along with high numbers of competing providers of that product. Businesses in these markets are price takers, and are driven towards lowering costs, de-skilling, or eliminating labor costs, which reduces the value ceiling of workers in the region. Wages falling below the level required to support household stability further limits leverage for them to negotiate for higher pay or improved working conditions. These constraints reinforce the Mi gap by reducing the ability of households to capture a greater share of regional economic value.

7.4 Long-Term Consequences for Wage Trajectories

The combined effects of industry structure, value leakage, and bargaining power feed directly into Ri. Regions that create and retain high-value economic activity tend to exhibit rising wage trajectories as firms reinvest, workers move into higher-paying roles, and industry composition upgrades over time. In contrast, regions with low value capture and concentrated low-margin sectors experience slower wage growth. As firms face tighter margins, fewer resources are available for wage increases, training, or workforce development. This predictable dynamic contributes to persistent divergence in Ri between high and low Ri counties.

7.5 Strategic Importance for the RSGI

From an analytical standpoint, Mi and Ri are not merely measures of household prosperity; they are proxies for the deeper structural characteristics that underlie value creation, value capture, and bargaining dynamics. Understanding these underlying mechanisms is essential for interpreting the index; high Mi and rising Ri signal regions with strong value-generation capacity and healthy labor market dynamics. Low Mi and low Ri signal regions where economic value is limited, leaks out of the region or is captured by firms operating as “Extractive” enterprises in the ecosystem (BCS, 2025).

By incorporating Mi and Ri, the RSGI provides a quantitative means of identifying where value retention and wage progression are insufficient to support long-term sustainability. This framework enables policymakers to identify not only current wage disparities but also the structural forces that produce and perpetuate them.

Section 8: Conclusion

The Regional Sustainability Gap Index (RSGI) offers a structured approach to assessing the long-term economic trajectory of Washington’s counties. By combining a region’s current wage altitude (Mi) with its wage-growth trajectory (Ri), the index offers a forward-looking assessment of whether local economies are positioned to sustain households, retain labor, and compete for future industry opportunities.

Mi captures the present capacity of a county’s wage structure to support household stability. Ri indicates whether that capacity is improving or deteriorating relative to the statewide benchmark. Together, the two measures reveal whether a county is closing the gap with the regions that drive Washington’s competitiveness or is falling further behind.

The analytical evidence suggests that counties with low Mi and declining Ri face the most significant long-term risk. These counties exhibit immediate affordability constraints, weakened incentives for human-capital investment, reduced attractiveness to high-value industries, and long-term structural narrowing. The Adams County example illustrates how these dynamics manifest mathematically and economically, with widening wage disparities producing predictable declines in workforce retention, household stability, and regional adaptability.

The RSGI does not replace existing economic indicators; rather, it supplements them by highlighting the wage dynamics most relevant to regional sustainability and well-being. For policymakers, the index provides a way to identify counties where divergence is

accelerating, where current conditions limit workforce retention, and where targeted intervention may be necessary to maintain long-term competitiveness.

By framing regional conditions through Mi and Ri, Washington State can adopt a more forward-looking, data-grounded approach to economic development. This helps better align workforce, infrastructure, and industry strategies with the wage trajectories that ultimately determine whether communities can sustain prosperity across generations. In this sense, reducing wage divergence is not only an economic development objective, but a strategy for strengthening statewide cohesion and long-term competitiveness.

Section 9: Future Research Directions

The RSGI provides a foundation for understanding long-term wage divergence across Washington's counties, but several areas warrant further investigation. First, the role of industry structure and ownership patterns in shaping Mi and Ri could be examined more directly. While current data capture wage outcomes, additional work linking wage trajectories to firm/property ownership, supply-chain position, and value-capture dynamics of the region of interest would provide deeper insight into the mechanisms driving regional divergence.

Second, future analysis could integrate regional price variation to refine estimates of household purchasing power. Although the RSGI focuses on relative earnings, incorporating cost-of-living adjustments at the county level may reveal additional differences in economic sustainability, particularly in regions where housing or service costs diverge from statewide norms.

Third, the relationship between wage trajectories and public sector capacity merits further study. Counties with low Mi and low Ri tend to exhibit constrained fiscal bases, limiting their ability to invest in workforce development, infrastructure, and economic diversification. Understanding how these fiscal constraints interact with wage dynamics may improve the design of targeted state-level interventions.

Fourth, additional extensions could link Mi and Ri trends to educational pipeline data, migration flows, and sector-level transitions. This would enable a more detailed examination of how wage divergence influences talent retention, skill cluster formation, and regional/state industry evolution.

Finally, the RSGI may be combined with complementary measures. Factors such as external ownership indicators, proprietor income trends, or firm formation rates would be viable complements in creating a broader diagnostic framework for regional

competitiveness. Such extensions could help identify where structural reforms or strategic investments would have the most significant effect on reversing long-term divergence.

Together, these areas of future research would enhance the analytical value of the RSGI and support more comprehensive regional strategies across Washington State.

11) Methods:

The *Regional Sustainability Gap Index (RSGI)* models a county's long-term wage sustainability as a function of two interdependent dynamics: Metropolitan Wage Divergence (Mi) and Relative Wage Growth (Ri). Together, these represent both a county's current economic position and its growth velocity within Washington State's competitive wage environment. This framing is consistent with theories of regional convergence and divergence (Partridge & Rickman, 2008; Rodríguez-Pose, 2018). The use of relative rather than absolute measures allows the RSGI to capture the "distance" between local and metropolitan trajectories, an approach aligned with comparative regional competitiveness frameworks (Martin & Sunley, 2006; Annoni & Dijkstra, 2019).

Conceptual Rationale

Factors that affect the median wage level in a region include the composition of its industries, the competitiveness of those industries in external markets, and the degree of rivalry among local firms. These conditions reflect the underlying industrial structure that determines how value is created, retained, and distributed across a regional labor market (Porter, 1990; Isserman, Feser, & Warren, 2009; Boschma & Iammarino, 2009).

Regional wage outcomes are also influenced by the mix of base (export-oriented) and import replacement (local-serving) industries (Jacobs, 1969; Besser, 2013; Goetz, Fleming, & Rupasingha, 2018). Research on regional lock-in suggests that areas dependent on externally owned or low-margin industries experience slower wage growth and weaker adaptive capacity, whereas diversified regions with endogenous firms tend to capture greater long-term gains (Martin & Sunley, 2006; Hassink, 2010; Hu & Hassink, 2020). The RSGI builds on this literature by focusing on how relative wage position and growth together signal whether a region's economic trajectory is sustainable. While household incomes are commonly used to evaluate economic growth in regions, in cases of economically distressed regions this significantly underrepresents the prosperity shortfall. Spurious income factors unrelated to wages such as Social Security payment, disability payments, pensions, food and housing assistance, as well as the likelihood of

multiple family members, multiple generations, and even non-family members' incomes reflect in household income metrics.

Data Inputs and Sources

Median household income data were obtained from the *U.S. Census Bureau's American Community Survey (ACS) 5-Year Estimates* for 2013 and 2023. Supplemental data were drawn from the *Washington State Employment Security Department (ESD) Median and Hourly Wages* dataset (2024 release) and cross-checked with *U.S. Census Local Employment Dynamics (LED) Quarterly Workforce Indicators*. These data sources provide consistent coverage across all 39 Washington counties. All wages were adjusted for inflation using the *Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS) Consumer Price Index for All Urban Consumers (CPI-U)* and projected forward using the *Congressional Budget Office's (CBO) 2025–2047 inflation forecasts*. These sources adhere to international standards for regional economic analysis (OECD, 2020; Sutton, Doran, & Burke, 2023).

Analysis:

Step 1. Metropolitan Wage Ratio (M_i)

Metropolitan Wage Ratio captures how far above or below King County a county's current median household income stands. It is defined as the ratio of the county's 2023 median wage to King County's 2023 median wage:

$$M_i = \frac{(Y_i, 2023)}{(Y_k, 2023)}$$

where $Y_{i,2023}$ is the 2023 median wage for county i , and $Y_{K,2023}$ is King County's 2023 median wage. This indicates how far below (or above) metropolitan wage level the county is projected to be 22 years into the future. For example, a value of $M_i = 0.28$ indicates that a county's median wage was only 28 percent of King County's in 2023. As the highest performer in terms of median wage of the 39 counties, it serves as a comparative benchmark for the other 38 counties.

Step 2: Deriving Relative Wage Growth (R_i)

The Relative Wage Growth Ratio (R_i) measures whether a county's wage growth over the last decade has kept pace with the state's most robust economy. In our analysis this is King County. It is defined as the ratio of each county's ten-year wage change to that of King County:

$$R_i = \frac{(1 + \Delta_i)}{(1 + \Delta_K)}$$

where Δ_i is the 2013–2023 percentage increase in median wage for county i , and Δ_K is the same measure for King County. A value of $R_i < 1$ indicates that the county’s wage growth has lagged behind King County’s over the last decade, while $R_i > 1$ suggests convergence or catch-up growth. This formulation captures relative momentum rather than absolute income, enabling the RSGL to identify counties improving their competitive position even if overall state growth is uneven (Partridge & Rickman, 2008; Rodríguez-Pose, 2018).

3. Composite Index (RSGL)

The RSGL integrates both the current Metro Wage Ratio and Relative Wage Growth into a single measure:

$$RSGL_i = \frac{(2M_i + R_i)}{3}$$

This weighting (two-thirds for wage difference and one-third for growth momentum) is to balance long-term positional competitiveness with short-term trajectory. There are two reasons that the weighting serves to make the index more relevant for observing this:

- 1) **Different Variances:** The two factors operate on different scales. Using Washington State County data, the standard deviations across the 39 counties are approximately:

$$\sigma(M_i) \approx 0.10 \text{ to } 0.12, \quad \sigma(R_i) \approx 0.18 \text{ to } 0.22.$$

The difference is roughly a 2:1 ratio. The weighting prevents the Relative Wage Growth from over-representing in the index.

- 2) **The Magnitude of Practical Impact:** While wage growth over the ten-year time frame is significant, members of communities are experiencing wage gap consequences now. For a worker, the annualized changes amount to a slight percentage difference in the conditions that they are experiencing now.

Visualization

Each county is plotted on a two-axis chart with M_i on the x-axis and R_i on the y-axis. The resulting

scatterplot reveals four quadrants of regional performance.

- Low M_i / Low R_i : Counties that are behind and falling further behind.
- Low M_i / High R_i : Counties that are behind but catching up.
- High M_i / Low R_i : Counties that are still ahead but losing ground.
- High M_i / High R_i : Counties that are ahead and accelerating.

This visual framework allows policymakers to understand both the level and rate of change in local economic altitude relative to Washington's dominant metro economy.

Kittitas County projected income growth chart.

- Blue (King County): rises from \$135,075 to about \$278,745.
- Orange (Kittitas County): grows from \$65,208 to roughly \$95,610.
- Gray (Inflation baseline): reaches \$124,945 by 2047, which is the level Kittitas would need to hit to maintain purchasing power.

Kittitas County version of the “Income Relative to Inflation and King County.”

Blue line: King County baseline (1.0 = reference).

- Gray line: Inflation-adjusted income target.
- Orange line: Kittitas County’s relative wage trajectory, declining from about 48% to 34% of King County’s level by 2047.

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